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AN ITERATION METHOD FOR MAPPINGS OF UNIFORMLY MONOTONE TYPE

We establish an iteration method which is useful for determining the solution of equations $Ax = b$ where A is a mapping, which is uniformly monotone and uniformly continuous. We also give an method to solve a variationally inequality.

1. INTRODUCTION

Let X be a Hilbert space, X^* the dual space; A is a (possibly) nonlinear mapping of X into X^* ; for $f \in X^*$ and $x \in X$, $f(x) = (f, x)$ denote the inner product.

DEFINITION 1.

(a) The mapping $A: X \rightarrow X^*$ is said to be monotone if and only if:

$$(Ax - Ay, x - y) \geq 0 \text{ for each } x, y \in X.$$

(b) The mapping A is said to be uniformly monotone if and only if there exists a real, positive and increasing function $m(t)$, $m(t) \rightarrow \infty$ for $t \rightarrow \infty$, and:

$$(Ax - Ay, x - y) \geq m(\|x - y\|).$$

(c) A is said to be strongly monotone if and only if $m(t) = mt^2$ ($m > 0$ is said to be the constant of monotonicity).

(d) A is said to be coercive if and only if:

$$\lim_{\|x\| \rightarrow \infty} \frac{(Ax, x)}{\|x\|} = 0.$$

DEFINITION 2. The mapping $A: X \rightarrow X^*$ is said to be radial-continuous if the real function $s(t) = (A(u+tv), v)$ is continuous at $[0, 1]$ for any fixed $u, v \in X$.

A fundamental statement about the solvability of the equation

$$(1) \quad Ax = b$$

with monotone mappings provides the fundamental theorem about monotone mappings by Browder and Minty (see for example [2]):

THEOREM 1. Suppose $A: X \rightarrow X^*$ is a monotone, radial-continuous, coercive mapping and X is a real separable, reflexive Banach space;

(a) For any $b \in X$ exists a solution of (1). The set of solutions is closed, bounded and convex.

(b) If additionally A is uniformly monotone mapping then for any $b \in X$ exists a unique solution x of (1).

2. A NEW ITERATION METHOD AND ESTIMATIONS

The basis for the error estimation of the following iteration method is the next theorem (see [1]):

THEOREM 2. Suppose $g(t)$ is (for $t > 0$) a positive, convex, strongly increasing function and $G'(t) = 1/g(t)$.

a) If $0 \leq t_{n+1} \leq t_n - g(t_n)$ ($n = 0, 1, \dots$) then $G(t_n) \leq G(t_0) - n$.

b) If $g'(t)$ is additionally continuous function then

$$G(t_n) \leq G(t_0) + n \lim_{t \rightarrow 0} \frac{\ln(1-g'(t))}{g'(t)}$$

THEOREM 3. Suppose that A is uniformly monotone and uniformly continuous mapping ($\|Ax - Ay\| \leq M\|x - y\|$, with a strongly increasing $M(t)$). Let $\frac{m(t)}{M^2(t)}$ be also increasing.

a) The succession $x_{n+1} := x_n - c_n J^{-1}(Ax_n - b)$ ($J: X \rightarrow X^*$ is a duality mapping) with

$$(2) \quad c_n = \frac{m(M^{-1}(\|Ax_n - b\|))}{\|Ax_n - b\|^2}$$

converges to the unique solution x^* of (1).

b) Let $g(t^2) = t^2 \frac{m(M^{-1}(\frac{m(t)}{t}))}{m(t)}$. If $g(t^2)$ is a differentiable function and $G'(t) = 1/g(t)$ then:

$$(3) \quad G(\|x_n - x^*\|^2) \leq G(h^2 \|Ax_0 - b\|) + n \lim_{t \rightarrow 0} \frac{h(1-g'(t))}{g'(t)}$$

($h(t)$ is the inverse function of $m(t)/t$).

PROOF. 1. Existence and uniqueness. A as a uniformly monotone mapping is

also coercive (see [2]). In accordance with Theorem 1 exists a unique solution x^* .

2. Convergence and estimations. For $Ax^* = b$ holds:

$$x_{n+1} - x^* = x_n - x^* - c_n J^{-1}(Ax_n - Ax^*).$$

We set $B = J^{-1}A$ and get

$$(4) \quad \|x_{n+1} - x^*\|^2 = \|x_n - x^*\|^2 - 2c_n (Bx_n - Bx^*, x_n - x^*) + c_n^2 \|Bx_n - Bx^*\|^2.$$

The hypothesis yields:

$$(Bx_n - Bx^*, x_n - x^*) = (Ax_n - Ax^*, x_n - x^*) \geq m(\|x_n - x^*\|)$$

and from $\|J^{-1}\| = 1$ it follows:

$$\|Bx_n - Bx^*\| \leq \|Ax_n - Ax^*\| = \|Ax_n - b\|.$$

Now we set $t_n := \|x_n - x^*\|$ and obtain from (4) the relation

$$(5) \quad t_{n+1}^2 \leq t_n^2 - 2c_n m(t_n) + c_n^2 \|Ax_n - b\|^2.$$

Now we put c_n given by (2) and obtain:

$$(6) \quad t_{n+1}^2 \leq t_n^2 - \frac{m(M^{-1}(\|Ax_n - b\|))}{\|Ax_n - b\|^2} (2m(t_n) - m(M^{-1}(\|Ax_n - b\|)))$$

and $\|Ax_n - b\| = \|Ax_n - Ax^*\| \leq M(\|x_n - x^*\|) = M(t_n)$ i.e.

$$(7) \quad M^{-1}(\|Ax_n - b\|) \leq t_n.$$

By means of the inequality of Schwarz we get:

$$\begin{aligned} m(\|x_n - x^*\|) &\leq (Bx_n - Bx^*, x_n - x^*) \leq \|Bx_n - Bx^*\| \cdot \|x_n - x^*\| \leq \\ &\leq \|Ax_n - Ax^*\| \cdot \|x_n - x^*\|, \end{aligned}$$

i.e.

$$(8) \quad m(t_n) \leq \|Ax_n - b\| t_n.$$

If $h(t)$ is inverse function of $m(t)/t$, it follows

$$(9) \quad t_n \leq h(\|Ax_n - b\|).$$

In consideration of (7) we obtain from (6)

$$t_{n+1}^2 \leq t_n^2 - \frac{m(M^{-1}(\|Ax_n - b\|))}{\|Ax_n - b\|^2} m(t_n).$$

If $m(t)/M^2(t)$ is an increasing function it follows from $\|Ax_n - b\| = [M(M^{-1}(\|Ax_n - b\|))]^2$ and (8) that:

$$t_{n+1}^2 \leq t_n^2 - t_n^2 \frac{m(M^{-1}(m(t_n)/t_n))}{m^2(t_n)} m(t_n),$$

i.e.

$$(10) \quad t_{n+1}^2 \leq t_n^2 - g(t_n^2)$$

with $g(t^2) = t^2 \frac{m(M^{-1}(m(t)/t))}{m(t)}$. This implies that $t_n \rightarrow 0$ for $n \rightarrow \infty$.

We set $t_n^2 = z_n$ and obtain from Theorem 2 that:

$$G(z_n) \leq G(z_0) + n \cdot \lim_{z \rightarrow 0} \frac{h(1-g'(z))}{g'(z)}$$

and if $g(z)$ is a differentiable function we get:

$$G(\|x_n - x_0\|^2) \leq G(h^2(\|Ax_0\|)) + n \cdot \lim_{t \rightarrow 0} \frac{h(1-g'(t))}{g'(t)} \quad (t \rightarrow 0)$$

q.e.d.

REMARK 1. In accordance with relations (9) and (10) it follows that:

$$\|x_n - x_0\| \leq \|x_n - x^*\| + \|x^* - x_0\| \leq 2\|x_0 - x^*\| \leq 2h(\|Ax_0 - b\|),$$

i.e. the requirements about the mapping A are only necessary at the cone K :

$$K = \{x: x \in X, \|x - x_0\| \leq 2h(\|Ax_0 - b\|)\}.$$

REMARK 2. If $m(t)/M^2$ is not increasing we can also prove the convergence of the described methods. We get:

$$t_{n+1}^2 \leq t_n^2 - \frac{m(M^{-1}(m(t_n)/t_n))}{M^2(t_n)} m(t_n) = t_n^2 - g_1(t_n^2).$$

2. VARIATIONALLY INEQUALITIES WITH MAPPINGS OF UNIFORMLY MONOTONE TYPE

Now we use our method to solve a variationally inequality with mappings of uniformly monotone and uniformly continuous type. Such variationally inequalities are used in the theory of optimization.

THEOREM 4. Suppose $A: M \rightarrow X^*$ is uniformly monotone and uniformly continuous mapping (like Theorem 3 and M is a subset of a separable Hilbert space H). Then exists a unique solution of the variationally inequality:

$$(Av-b, v-u) \geq 0$$

for all $v \in M$, with $u \in M$ and $b \in X^*$ and the succession

$$x_{n+1} := x_n - c_n J^{-1}(Ax_n - b)$$

(J is the duality mapping),

$$c_n = \frac{m(M^{-1}(\|Ax_n - b\|))}{\|Ax_n - b\|^2}$$

converges to the unique solution x of (1).

PROOF. We show that the solution of $(Av-b, v-u) \geq 0$ for all $v \in M$ is equivalent to solution of the equation

$$Au = b.$$

a) Let be $Au = b$. We define: $A'x := Ax - b$. then is $A'u = 0$ and $(A'v - A'u, v-u) = (Av - Au, v-u) \geq 0$, i.e. A' is also monotone, so follow that

$$(Av-b, v-u) = (A'v - 0, v-u) = (A'v - A'u, v-u) \geq 0$$

for all $v \in M$.

b) Now let be $(Av-b, v-u) \geq 0$ for all $v \in M$. We define: $v_t := u + tv$, $t > 0$, then is

$$0 \leq (Av_t - b, v-u) = (Av_t - b, u+tv-u) = t(Av_t - b, v),$$

$$0 \leq (Av_t - b, v).$$

A uniformly continuous mapping is also radial continuous. So we get for $t \rightarrow 0$

$$0 \leq (Au-b, v).$$

This inequality is fulfilled for any v ; also with $(-v)$. So we get $0 \leq (Au-b, -v) = -(Au-b, v)$ and finally $Au = b$. Theorem 1 implies that there exists a unique solution u of the equation $Au = b$ and therefore for our variationally inequality. In the end we get from Theorem 3 that the sequence (x_n) converges to the unique solution x .

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